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**Methodology for assessing the development of ecological and economic systems
and civil security based on AI**

The modern world is facing unprecedented challenges, such as war, climate change, depletion of resources, growth of cybercrime, etc. These challenges make assessing ecological and economic systems and civil security more critical. The development of a methodology for evaluating the state of development of environmental and economic systems and civil security (physical, psychological, economic, and cyber security) based on the implementation of artificial intelligence technologies may include the development of a methodology for assessing the development of ecological and economic systems and a method for evaluating the development of civil security, namely: physical security, psychological security, economic security, cyber security. All this can be based on introducing artificial intelligence technologies; that is, artificial intelligence should help assess the development of ecological and economic systems and civil security. To qualitatively approach such a process, it is necessary to analyze what has already been done along this path. Figure 1 shows the number of publications devoted to using artificial intelligence to assess the development of ecological and economic systems. The number of publications on this topic is growing significantly. This means that the relevance of such studies is relatively high, and therefore, scientific interest in them is growing. We will analyze research in this area and assess the development of civil security.

Price-Smith (Price-Smith, 2009) deeply explored the topic of ecological, economic and civil security (primarily physical) and put forward the main argument that threats to physical security in the form of diseases pose a significant threat to national security, undermining prosperity, stability and international relations state Moreover, wars increase the threat to physical security.

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King et al. (King et al., 2018) characterized cyber security threats from the point of view of maliciousness and proposed a methodology for assessing human maliciousness in the cyber sphere. Rose (Rose A., 2017) analyzed economic sustainability from a multifaceted point of view, considering social, environmental and security factors. Based on this, he proposed a methodology for measuring economic sustainability. In addition, he proved the connection between economic sustainability and human development. Hathaway et al. (Hathaway et al., 2012) explain how national cyber security can be understood. They examined how different countries integrate their respective conceptions of national security and cybersecurity and offer a methodology that explains what "national cybersecurity " might entail. Pryor et al. (Prior, 2014) consider physical security as a system of components, thus contributing to its assessment, and present a methodology for measuring psychological resilience. Al-Dosari and others. (Al-Dosari, 2023) consider a method for evaluating the implementation of "green cyber security ", based on which they found that "green cyber security " will allow to systematically seek and promote innovations made possible by intelligent environmental technologies to avoid CO2 emissions. Gou et al. (Gou, 2022) investigated civil safety and found that system dynamics provides a great deal of theoretical and technical support for hazard detection and accident prevention. This means that system dynamics is an essential method for studying system security. Barnett (Barnett, 2001) examines how environmental problems pose a security threat. He criticizes the idea that ecological security is conditioned by solving environmental problems, suggesting that it is more about the power of actors to ensure such security. Bokhari et al. (Bokhari, 2023) explored the capabilities of artificial intelligence. They concluded that it could potentially enhance cyber capabilities and cyber security of nation-states, local governments, and non-governmental organizations through e-governance. Garcia (Garcia, 2008) developed a methodology for designing and evaluating physical security systems. The methodology covers various aspects such as threat assessment, security technologies, procedures and response plans.

From the analysis of previous studies, although research was conducted in the declared directions, they acquired a partial character, that is, they related only to

specific directions, which is natural. At the same time, artificial intelligence technologies have yet to become widespread as the basis of such analysis. But in this case, the task is to develop a comprehensive methodology for assessing the development of ecological and economic systems and civil security, including physical, psychological, economic, and cyber security.

Implementing artificial intelligence technologies is crucial because it can significantly facilitate the task. After all, their use helps both the development of ecological and economic systems and civil security and their evaluation. Artificial intelligence can provide extensive analytical capabilities. Artificial intelligence is an essential component of modern research, and although it has some limitations, it still becomes an indispensable assistant. Let's analyze in detail what benefits artificial intelligence can bring when assessing the state of development of ecological and economic systems and civil security.

Evaluation of the development of ecological and economic systems based on the introduction of artificial intelligence technologies

Thanks to machine learning algorithms, artificial intelligence can analyze vast volumes of data about the environment's state and economic indicators. At the same time, deep learning models can reveal complex relationships between various ecological and economic factors affecting the environment and the economy. For example, by analyzing pollution from CO₂ emissions and other pollutants, artificial intelligence systems can predict damage to the environment, population and economy. This allows you to get the basis for adopting the best strategies for reducing pollution and increasing the sustainability of economic systems.

Another important option for using artificial intelligence in assessment is predicting climate change, which can affect various ecological and economic spheres. One direction may be analysing data from multiple sources, including satellite images, sensors on the ground, and the Internet. This can make obtaining a complete picture of ecological and economic development possible.

Also, artificial intelligence can help optimise using natural and energy resources. Optimization algorithms will allow for finding more efficient ways of using energy and

other resources. This reduces their losses and contributes to the sustainable development of the state.

In addition to the above, artificial intelligence can help evaluate waste management and secondary resources. Its algorithms can recognize materials that can be recycled and then optimize recycling processes. This will contribute to the efficient use of resources and reduce the negative impact on the environment.

AI machine learning systems can help predict environmental and economic crises. They can analyze previous scenarios of environmental and economic crises and provide recommendations for preventing similar situations in the future.

Another important area of possible use of artificial intelligence in assessment is environmental monitoring with data collection. Sensors and IoT devices can collect vast amounts of environmental data, which artificial intelligence systems will then analyze. This will allow in real time to quickly react to environmental changes and take adequate measures to manage such changes.

Artificial intelligence can also help detect environmental and economic violations and illegal use of nature. Its algorithms can analyze harmful emissions and economic indicators data and automatically notify relevant authorities of possible violations. This will contribute to increased control over compliance with environmental norms and economic rules and stimulate the implementation of an improved regulatory framework.

Now, let's consider how artificial intelligence can be helpful in evaluation with an emphasis on economic systems. Artificial intelligence machine learning systems can analyze large volumes of economic data, including indicators of GDP, employment, inflation, etc. This will make it possible to assess the economy's state more quickly and accurately and identify trends occurring in it.

Artificial intelligence algorithms can detect complex relationships between various economic factors and predict the consequences of these factors. For example, it is possible to predict the level of consumer demand based on economic and social data. Such an analysis will make it possible to make better strategic decisions in finance, business and politics.

Artificial intelligence algorithms can also help in the identification and forecasting of both economic risks and economic crises. This happens by analyzing historical data and identifying patterns that may indicate approaching economic crises. This will make it possible to make management decisions regarding measures to prevent crises or reduce their consequences.

Another important aspect is the use of artificial intelligence in forecasting economic development. With the help of algorithms, you can analyze economic indicators and find indicators that indicate possible development paths. This will help formulate strategies to stimulate economic growth and increase competitiveness. In addition, you can predict market trends and find possible ways to respond to them. Artificial intelligence algorithms can analyze data from goods and services markets, financial markets and other sources. This will allow companies and government bodies to adapt their economic strategies to changes in the market and maximize their profits.

Artificial intelligence can help in financial management. Data on financial transactions can be analyzed, and risks can be assessed to make investment and portfolio management recommendations. This will help avoid financial losses and maximize income.

In addition to the above, artificial intelligence can help predict the cost of goods and services for consumers and market analysts. Analysis of prices, demand, and market events allows you to anticipate future changes in value. Based on this, companies can make pricing and inventory decisions.

Also, artificial intelligence is a tool for supply chain management. Analysis of demand, inventory and transportation data will allow obtaining an information base for optimizing supply processes. As a result, costs can be reduced, and supply chain efficiency can be increased.

And finally, artificial intelligence allows you to forecast inflation and exchange rates. Analysis of economic data on global trends will provide information to understand the factors affecting the value of money. Such opportunities will allow for the management of financial risks and the development of strategies for maintaining the stability of the national economy. After analyzing large volumes of data, it is

possible to make predictions about the direction of market development. Based on this, business structures and government bodies can plan their actions and adapt to changes in the economic environment.

Assessment of the development of civil security systems (including physical, psychological, economic security and cyber security) based on the implementation of artificial intelligence technologies

Artificial intelligence technologies for analyzing big data can become essential for assessing civil security systems, which is vital in military operations and emergencies. They can help identify potential threats and vulnerabilities in various aspects of civil security. For example, with the help of analysis of video and audio materials by artificial intelligence, it is possible to detect suspicious activity or a restless state among citizens, which may indicate some extraordinary events. Algorithms can analyze a large data stream from sensors and surveillance cameras to detect anomalous processes. These can be unexpected changes in traffic flow, unusual activity in public places, etc.

In addition, artificial intelligence technologies can be used to predict future threats to civil security. For example, retrospective analysis can help identify patterns that will indicate the possibility of specific types of threats to civil security in the future. This allows for the implementation of effective measures to prevent civil danger.

In the field of psychological security, algorithms can analyze data on citizens' behaviour and emotional state. That is, they can detect changes in the psychological state, which can indicate possible dangerous events or situations of threat to civil safety.

Analysis of economic data can help in assessing economic stability and potential risks. It can detect economic indicators that indicate an increase or decrease in threats to economic security.

In cyber security, artificial intelligence algorithms can analyze data from internet networks and systems to detect cyber-attacks and threats. They can analyze changes in network activity patterns that may indicate potential cyberattacks or vulnerabilities. This will help protect against cybercrime and maintain information security.

It is also essential to consider the interrelationships between different security aspects, which may influence each other. For example, an economic crisis can lead to an increase in the level of crime or psychological disorders in society. Therefore, the analysis of integrated data with the help of artificial intelligence can help to assess these relationships and obtain a tool for making appropriate decisions.

Data evaluation can contribute to improving decision-making processes in managing the physical security of the population. That is, recommendations can be provided based on the analysis of physical security data, which helps to make quick and informed decisions to ensure it. This approach contributes to the optimization of state resources and effectively responds to potential threats to physical security.

Integrating various data sources with the help of artificial intelligence will help assess the state of civil security. For example, combining digital data from video surveillance cameras, social networks, special sensors, and other sources can create a comprehensive assessment of the situation, allowing an understanding of the civil security context based on which balanced decisions can be made.

In addition to the above, ensuring the protection and confidentiality of data used to evaluate the development of civil security systems is essential. Applying the necessary data encryption and protection methods is critical in using artificial intelligence technologies when evaluating data for security purposes. This prevents unwanted intrusions and abuses.

Thus, using artificial intelligence to assess the state of development of ecological and economic systems and civil security is very important because it will contribute to the stability and security of society. At the same time, artificial intelligence automates data collection and processing, detects complex patterns in data, predicts risks, and develops recommendations for governments, businesses and public organizations to overcome problems.

Approaches to the development of methods for assessing the state of development of ecological and economic systems and civil security based on the implementation of artificial intelligence technologies

The development of a methodology for assessing the state of development of ecological and economic systems and civil security based on the implementation of artificial intelligence technologies has specific approaches that must be described.

First, it is necessary to determine the indicators using such a method. Then, the collection of data on the relevant indicators proceeds directly. It includes the collection of:

1. Environmental data. These can be indicators of the quality of air, water, soil, forests, biodiversity, etc.
2. Economic data. These can be GDP indicators, unemployment level, investments in nature protection projects, etc.
3. Civil security data. It can be statistics of losses related to military actions, statistics of crime and cybercrime, and indicators of the physical and psychological health of the population.

After data collection comes the stage of their analysis. This stage should include:

1. Using deep learning algorithms to analyze large volumes of data.
2. Identifying trends and anomalies that may indicate potential threats or opportunities for improvement.

After data analysis, the stage of modelling and forecasting follows. It includes:

1. Creation of models for forecasting future states of ecological and economic systems and civil safety.
2. Using neural networks for more accurate forecasting.

The next stage will be risk assessment. It includes:

1. Risk analysis for different development scenarios.
2. Determination of the most critical factors that affect the security and stability of systems.

After the risk assessment, further recommendations can be developed for governments, businesses and civil society organizations based on the analysis and forecasts. It is also necessary to implement strategies to reduce risks and improve the health of systems.

How are artificial intelligence technologies implemented? Artificial intelligence is needed for:

1. Automation of data collection and processing. It can collect data using sensors, drones, or the Internet of Things.
2. Deep learning. This is needed to analyze data and create predictive models.
3. Natural Language Processing (NLP). This is required for analyzing textual data such as news, social networks, reports, etc.

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